

D2.2 Green Deal Data Space CGD node

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Executive summary

This deliverable corresponds to the one of the task “T2.4 The FAIR and CARE Green Deal Data Space CGD node” of the more4nature project.

The purpose of this deliverable is to illustrate a demonstration on how the Citizen Generated Data (CGD) from the more4nature project can be included in the AD4GD (All Data for the Green Deal) prototype of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) and how those data can be accessed from the dataspace. This demonstration reflexes the state of the art in the Data Space connector technology and how it could be used to incorporate CGD. The Data Space support centre defines a series of technical and non-technical building blocks that constitutes a Data Space. This demonstration focuses on the technical building blocks only. The governance aspects of a GDDS are still to be defined and as a consequence cannot be covered in this demonstration.

In the future, the final technical report of this Project will include how the more4nature project will set up its own Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC), connected to the more official Green Deal Data Space that the EU project SAGE is going to develop in the following 2.5 years.

Table of Contents

- EXECUTIVE SUMMARY..... 4**
- 1 INTRODUCTION 10**
 - 1.1 THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL 10
 - 1.2 DATA SPACE 10
 - 1.2.1 *Data space building blocks*11
 - 1.2.2 *Dataspace Protocol (DSP) as an implementation of Technical Building Blocks* 13
 - 1.3 GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE..... 15
- 2 DEMONSTRATOR OF A CGD IN THE GDDS.....17**
 - 2.1 COLLABORATION WITH AD4GD 17
 - 2.2 ECLIPSE DATASPACE CONNECTOR 17
 - 2.3 INTEGRATION OF CGD IN THE GDDS 18
 - 2.4 ACCESS TO CGD FROM THE GDDS CLIENT SIDE 19
- 3 CONCLUSION..... 24**
- 4 REFERENCES..... 25**

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Classifications of the Data Space Building Blocks into Business & Organizational, and Technical ones. 12

Figure 2: Classifications of the Data Space Technical Building Blocks (orange rectangles signal the building block covered by this deliverable to enable data exchange)..... 13

Figure 3: Control and data plane interactions 15

Figure 4: AD4GD GDDS architecture. The left hand side illustrates the implementation of the data plane and the right hand side the deployment of the control plane 18

Figure 5: Four main steps required to get a data transfer in the data space 19

Figure 6: Access to the Ad4GD datasets catalogue.....20

Figure 7: List of the datasets offered by the federated catalogue20

Figure 8: Data Space Protocol steps that start in contract negotiation and ends in the actual file download20

Figure 9: Data Space Protocol steps as seen from the web browser debugger tool..... 21

Figure 10: Root element of a SensorThings API resource offer by the dataspace 21

Figure 11: Selection of a particular DataStream, request of the observations that are ordered by time and filtered to remove noData values (in TAPIS arrows represents the direction of the dependency, that it is the opposite of the data flow)22

Figure 12: Water level changes in time, for a period of 3 months on a citizen science sensor in a lake..... 23

Glossary of terms

Term	Definition
Citizen Generated Data (CGD)	Data streams generated through Citizen Science.
Citizen Science (CS)	Citizen Science refers to the involvement of civilian actors in various forms of collaborative data and knowledge generation, including science-driven projects, initiatives to democratize science and policy via science citizenship, civic and community-based (environmental) monitoring, and citizen observatories.
Citizen Observatory (CO)	A particular form of CS that provides the means for new forms of interactions between policy-makers, the general public and the scientific community. CO involves ICT-facilitated bi- and multidirectional data and information flows, typically linked to participatory processes in environmental monitoring and governance.
Collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance (ECA)	Citizens and communities - in partnership with relevant authorities - collaborate in promoting, monitoring and acting to protect the environment.
Compliance	Act of submitting or yielding power to an authority and doing what is expected or required under a rule system enacted by that authority.
GAIA-X	European initiative that enables a federated and secure data infrastructure, whereby data are shared, with users retaining control over their data access and usage. It enables the creation of links between many cloud service providers in a wider, transparent and fair ecosystem to drive the European Data economy of tomorrow.
Metadata	Information about a resource (Source: ISO 19115-1)

Table of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AD4GD	All Data for Green Deal
API	Application Programming Interface
ATOS	ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL
CGD	Citizen Generated Data
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DIDs	Decentralized Identifiers
DSP	DataSpace Protocol
DSSC	Data Space Support Center
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connector
EDWG	Eclipse Dataspace Working Group
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
OAuth	Open Authorization
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PSNC	Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
SAGE	The Data Space for a Sustainable Green Europe
SDIs	Spatial Data Infrastructures
STA	SensorThing API
TAPIS	Tables from APIs
TCK	Technology Compatibility Kit

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1 Introduction

The more4nature project is contributing to the Environmental Compliance Assurance (ECA) with current environmental policies including the ones directly related with the European Green Deal. For the success of the European Green Deal monitoring approaches based on environmental data from different sources such as remote sensing, official in-situ monitoring and citizen generated data should be used.

1.1 The European Green Deal

The European Green Deal stands as the European Commission's roadmap to transform society and economy towards combating climate change and its derived challenges. Through this comprehensive strategy, the EU aspires to become the world's first resource-efficient and competitive economy, achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 [1].

The Green Deal targets a very diverse range of topics of great importance for the health of our planet including climate change, circular economy, pollution, biodiversity and deforestation. These priorities relate to established European directives such as the 2030 Biodiversity Strategy and the recently approved Nature Restoration Law or the European Climate Law, as an integral part of the Commission's strategy to implement the Paris Agreement and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

Data, services and digital technologies play a pivotal role in realizing this green transformation. The Green Deal advocates for accessible and interoperable data to be at the heart of innovation and recognizes that edge computing, the Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence and other digital datasets are critical enablers of impactful climate policies.

1.2 Data Space

A data space¹ is a distributed system defined by a governance framework that enables trustworthy data transactions between participants while supporting trust and data sovereignty. A data space is implemented by one or more infrastructures and supports one or more use cases [2].

For example, in the mobility domain, use cases might entail traffic management in smart cities, end-to-end intermodal mobility services as well as detailed traffic infrastructure monitoring. In data spaces, compliance to legal provisions regarding the management and use of data is ensured; data subjects and holders can control their data and its subsequent use.

Unlike traditional centralized data storage solutions, a data space is decentralized: data remains with its original owner, who controls access and usage, while interoperability and standardized exchange protocols ensure seamless collaboration.

¹ Dataspace in one word and data space in two words means the same in this deliverable.

The key characteristics of a data space are:

- **Decentralized Control:** Data stays with its provider, who decides who can access it, under what conditions, and at what cost.
- **Interoperability:** Data spaces are designed to connect diverse data infrastructures, enabling systems with different formats and standards to communicate and share data efficiently.
- **Security and Governance:** Robust security measures and clear governance frameworks ensure data privacy, compliance (e.g., GDPR), and trust among participants.
- **Standardization:** Use of agreed-upon standards and protocols for data exchange, ensuring consistency and reliability.
- **Ecosystem Approach:** Data spaces foster collaboration across sectors (e.g., health, energy, and mobility), regions, or thematic domains, supporting innovation and new services.

In that respect, data spaces are an evolution of the spatial data infrastructures (SDIs). SDIs and data spaces enable interoperability by using most of the same standards for data sharing and data processing. SDIs were also decentralized systems. While, SDIs were mainly offering open data for the public administrations to other parties, including companies and members of the public, data spaces include companies and members of the public in the ecosystem enabling a digital economy. In that respect, personal data from members of the public is better protected when include it in a data space.

implemented and combined with other building blocks to achieve the functionality of a data space.

1.2.1 Data space building blocks

The Data Space Support Center (DSSC) adopted the concept of building blocks to break data spaces into manageable smaller pieces. Building blocks are basic units or components that can be

The DSSC 17 building blocks can be divided in 6 categories (Figure 1); ranging from business, governance, and legal to technical building blocks on data interoperability, trust, and data value.

Figure 1: Classifications of the Data Space Building Blocks into Business & Organizational, and Technical ones.

Technical capabilities are structured according to three pillars (Figure 2):

- **Data Interoperability:** The capabilities needed for data exchange are semantic models, data formats, and interfaces (APIs). This also includes functionalities for provenance and traceability.
- **Data Sovereignty and Trust:** Capabilities needed for identifying participants and datasets in a data space, establishing trust and the possibility to define and enforce policies for access & usage control.
- **Data Value Creation Enablers:** Capabilities used to enable value-creation in a data space, e.g. by registering and discovering data offerings or services and providing value-creation services.

Figure 2: Classifications of the Data Space Technical Building Blocks (orange rectangles signal the building block covered by this deliverable to enable data exchange)

This deliverable is focused on the technical building blocks and, in particular, the ones that enable data exchange.

1.2.2 Dataspace Protocol (DSP) as an implementation of Technical Building Blocks

The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) has released the Dataspace Protocol (DSP). This protocol specifies that:

- Datasets are deployed as DCAT Catalogues and usage control is expressed as ODRL Policies.
- Agreements govern data usage are syntactically expressed and electronically negotiated.
- Datasets are accessed using Transfer Process Protocols.

The DSP only specifies the generic elements (sometime referred as the control plane). The APIs/technical interfaces for the actual data exchange are data space-specific (sometime referred as the data plane).

The DSP is undergoing the Eclipse Specification Process within the Eclipse Dataspace Working Group (EDWG) to combine the specification document with a Technology Compatibility Kit (TCK) to test compliance of specific implementations of the Dataspace Protocol with the specification.

The control plane implements a number of technical building blocks. They are:

- **Identity and Attestations:** The exchange of an identity and other relevant attestations. This is likely to include a credential indicating that someone is participating in a particular data space (thus complying with the relevant

rulebook). We propose to use the W3C Verifiable Credentials standard for this purpose.

- **Catalogue Entries:** These provide metadata describing the available Data Products in a catalogue. We propose using the W3C DCAT standard for this purpose.
- **Policies and Contract Negotiation:** A data provider defines the access and usage policies for its Data Products. This can be defined using the ODRL standard. Based on the exchanged identities and attestation, and using any policy information points, a decision can be reached on whether or not to grant access to the data.
- **Management of the Transfer Process:** Finally, the actual data exchange can take place (in the data plane). The control plane is still interfacing with the data plane, e.g., to ensure the proper execution of the agreed policies (policy enforcement).

The data plane, unlike other elements of the Dataspace Protocol (a.k.a Control Plane, e.g. Catalog Protocol, Contract Negotiation Protocol), is domain-specific, having its own and specific data exchange protocol (e.g. described in a particular OpenAPI, or using general-purpose data exchange protocols).

In practice the both the control plane and the data plane are implemented by a component called “dataspace connector”. The following figure (Figure 3) shows the functionalities that the dataspace connector implements:

- **Cataloguing (catalogue protocol):** allows for discovering datasets presents in the Data Space.
- **Contract Negotiation (contract negotiation protocol):** allows for verifying if the user has the rights to access the dataset.
- **Transfer process management (transfer process protocol):** allows for requesting the way in which the dataset will be transferred to the user.
- **Data exchange (data exchange protocol):** allows executing the transfer of the dataset to the user.

Figure 3: Control and data plane interactions

1.3 Green Deal Data Space

The Green Deal Data Space (GD DS) is a major European initiative designed to accelerate the goals of the European Green Deal by enabling secure, interoperable, and trusted sharing of high-value environmental and sustainability-related data across sectors and borders. The GD DS is one of the common European data spaces defined by the European Strategy for Data and dedicated to support the priority actions of the Green Deal in terms of sharing high value and high quality datasets for biodiversity preservation, zero pollution, circular economy, climate change mitigation, deforestation reduction, smart mobility and environmental compliance. It emerges as the intersection between the green and the digital transformation. Industries, governments, and researchers will benefit from easy sharing of high quality, interoperable data and derived services, while data holders and providers maintain control over who and how access is provided.

The GDDS will therefore be established on solid foundations of technologies, governance and trust, respecting European values and applying the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (FAIR). It is also a goal to interconnect currently fragmented and dispersed cross-sectorial data from diverse origins, including private, public sectors and citizen generated data, in support of the Green Deal priorities. It is therefore one of the most diverse and transversal European common data spaces.

The ultimate goal is to offer an interoperable, trusted digital environment for high value and high quality data, and a set of legislative, administrative and contractual rules that determine the rights of access to and use of the data. This will benefit businesses, consumers, government and citizens, connecting public and private data system of systems and allowing reuse of data across borders and sectors within the defined trusted space.

2 Demonstrator of a CGD in the GDDS

2.1 Collaboration with AD4GD

The EU Horizon Europe AD4GD project has the mission to co-create and shape the GDDS as an open hub for FAIR data and standards-based services that support the key priorities of pollution, biodiversity and climate change. AD4GD has been conducting research and innovation on data spaces and how to use them in coordination of OGC services and APIs.

The task 2.4 of more4nature started to collaborate with AD4GD project to set up a demonstrator that provides access to Citizen Generated Data (CGD) in the Green Deal Data Space.

Several future scenarios including the possibility that more4nature sets up its own data connector ensuring that more4nature is able to manage the CGD that is going to be shared in the Green Deal Data Space, and providing access to the data in the three thematic areas (Zero Pollution /Biodiversity /Deforestation) are considered.

This deliverable demonstrates how the CGD, included in an OGC SensorThing API (STA), can be a dataset in the GDDS.

2.2 Eclipse Dataspace Connector

The Eclipse Dataspace Components provide a framework for sovereign inter-organizational data sharing. They implement the IDS Dataspace Protocol (DSP) as well as relevant protocols associated with GAIA-X. The Eclipse Dataspace Components are designed in an extensible way in order to support alternative protocols and integrate in various ecosystems.

Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) is an open source framework hosted by the Eclipse Foundation for building secure, globally-scalable data-sharing services. EDC provides highly customizable components for creating control planes, data planes, decentralized identity systems, and federated data catalogues. Backed by leading companies and cloud providers, EDC gives developers the tools they need to deliver innovative solutions for data exchange networks.

EDC is a system implementing the concept of dataspace. EDC is a set of components that enable developers to create dataspace using the following building blocks:

- Identity service for managing and verifying organizational credentials using Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and W3C Verifiable Credentials or OAuth2 tokens.
- Catalogue service for publishing and securing datasets that can be shared with other organizations.
- Control plane services for the automated creation and processing of data usage agreements that grant access to data.

- Data plane and monitoring services for initiating and managing data transfers using off-the-shelf protocols such as HTTP, Kafka, cloud object storage, or virtually any other technology.

EDC components are standards-based and implement the Dataspace Protocol Specification and Decentralized Claims Protocol Specification (<https://eclipse-edc.github.io/documentation/>).

2.3 Integration of CGD in the GDDS

AD4GD has adopted the last version of the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) and PSNC (Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center) has implemented some extensions to it. Using EDC, AD4GD has created a data space with two nodes that implements a federated catalogue and the control plane. The first node is operated by PSNC and the other is operated by ATOS (both partners in the AD4GD project). The data is provided by the ATOS EDC but in order to demonstrate how the data space works, the access to the data is done through the PSNC node. The following figure (Figure 5) illustrates this setup.

Figure 4: AD4GD GDDS architecture. The left hand side illustrates the implementation of the data plane and the right hand side the deployment of the control plane

As the first step to demonstrate how to integrate citizen science data in the GDDS, more4nature has collaborated with AD4GD. In this collaboration, more4nature has given to AD4GD some data to ingest in a Sensor Things API instance that is part of the data plane of their implementation of the GDDS. This data should become available through their EDC catalogue.

The access to the server side involves several HTTP requests, some of them asynchronous (see Figure 4):

1. Data or service discovery in a federated catalogue
2. Contract negotiation
3. Request transfer
4. Actual data download

Figure 5: Four main steps required to get a data transfer in the data space

In order to execute all these API calls, a client side tool that is able to hide and encapsulate the complexities of these steps needs to be developed.

2.4 Access to CGD from the GDDS Client side

Tables from APIs (TAPIS) (www.github.com/grumets/tapis) are going to be used as a client to demonstrate how to access data coming from the data space. TAPIS is an API explorer and a table manager. TAPIS reads data and metadata from some supported APIs and some data file formats and structures the data as tables that can be managed and transformed. Internally, everything is a table that has columns that represents fields and rows that represent records. TAPIS is connected to the MiraMon Map Browser (www.github.com/grumets/MiraMonMapBrowser) to represent spatial records. We have extended TAPIS to support the Data Space Protocol used by the EDC.

In order to demonstrate how the EDC works, it is needed to start by connecting to the EDC federated catalogue (<https://ad4gd-catalog-edc.dashboard-siba.store>) and get a list of datasets that are accessible.

query	-	
<input type="checkbox"/> contractnegotiations	-	"@id": "74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> contractnegotiations	-	"type": "CONSUMER",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c	-	"protocol": "dataspace-protocol-http",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c	-	"state": "FINALIZED",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c	-	"counterPartyId": "provider",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c	-	"counterPartyAddress": "https://ad4gd-provider-edc.dashboard-siba.store/protocol",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c	-	"callbackAddresses": [],
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c	-	"createdAt": 1747415720167,
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c	-	"contractAgreementId": "ee47d610-086d-44c4-a2c1-316f95ff6ddd",
<input type="checkbox"/> transferprocesses	-	"@context": {
<input checked="" type="radio"/> transferprocesses	-	"vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28	-	"edc": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/",
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28	-	"odr1": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odr1/2/"
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28	-	}
<input checked="" type="radio"/> 60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28	-	}
<input checked="" type="radio"/> dataaddress	-	
<input type="checkbox"/> public	-	
<input checked="" type="radio"/> public	-	

Figure 9: Data Space Protocol steps as seen from the web browser debugger tool

In this case, the downloaded dataset is not a file, but the response of the root element of a SensorThings API resource that lists the types of entities available and the URL to get to them (Figure 10).

OGC query URL: <https://ad4gd-provider-edc.dashboard-siba.store/public>

Show row numbers Show self and navigation links

name	url
1 Observations	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Observations
2 Datastreams	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Datastreams
3 FeaturesOfInterest	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/FeaturesOfInterest
4 HistoricalLocations	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/HistoricalLocations
5 Locations	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Locations
6 ObservedProperties	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/ObservedProperties
7 Sensors	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Sensors
8 Things	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api_appos.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Things

Figure 10: Root element of a SensorThings API resource offer by the dataspace

In TAPIS, it is possible to continue exploring the data by selecting a datastream that represents, for example, the water height in a lake. And then do a “sort by” to ensure chronological order and filter out values less than -600 which are only noData values.

Figure 11: Selection of a particular DataStream, request of the observations that are ordered by time and filtered to remove noData values (in TAPIS arrows represents the direction of the dependency, that it is the opposite of the data flow)

Figure 12: Water level changes in time, for a period of 3 months on a citizen science sensor in a lake

3 Conclusion

This demonstration explains the main components of the dataspace created in the AD4GD prototype, and illustrates both sides: server and client, respectively, for integrating CGD in the AD4GD prototype of the GDDS , and accessing CGD from that dataspace.

The demonstration illustrates how a dataset (e.g. a Citizen Science Data from the more4nature project) is included in the AD4GD prototype of the Green Deal Data Space and how those data is accessed from that dataspace. In the future, we would like to set up our own EDC, integrated in the official Green Deal Data Space that the EU project SAGE is going to develop in the following 2.5 years. This deliverable contains illustrations of the conducted demonstration.

4 References

[1] <https://ad4gd.eu/what-is-the-green-deal-data-space/>

[2] Data Spaces Glossary 3.0 Mar 5. 2024, Data Spaces Support Centre, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/15x6WHHGSoG4ZuXQw8u3AinpJrgbydriL>

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